

ANALYSIS OF IMAGES IN THE NOVEL "BAZAR" BY
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Annotation: This article analyzes the events in the novel, the life of the characters and reveals their role in the essence of the work.

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Like other works by Khurshid Dostmuhammad, the novel "Bazar" has a significant place in Uzbek literature. "Bazaar" is a novel that tries to interpret human life in the market. The protagonist of the work is Fozilbek, who worked in the seven pink markets, and his father. The young man, who will live with his brothers, sisters, father and stepmother, does not work anywhere, does not come from the market. 'he said. He was the youngest in the family, and when his mother gave birth to him, the mother left this bright world. He grows up thirsty for this kind of love, he goes to the market in search of wisdom and bathing in his thoughts. Like the poet who seeks his inspiration, the family of the young man, who is always carefree, thoughtful, and in public, is burning with the desire to marry him and make a head out of him. He does not want to start a family in such a way that he hopes to find his successor only through his own heart, if possible, through his own consciousness. Fozilbek's actions and thoughts at the beginning of the work are really true. and the reader, who devotes his whole life to the realization of himself and to himself. Not only the sun in Fozilbek's life, but also some sad and heartbreaking events, intriguing plots bring new blood to the work, which is in the foreground. The character sees his happiness in the image of Qadriya. There were so many symbols, images, gestures hidden in their endless

conversations ... Even the girl who understands the most incomprehensible guy d arveshona was not far from thoughts, nor could she be. People never stop going to the MARKET where they create and suffer. ,, Because the market area is low, the level is a-much lower than the surrounding area. He who loses a little vigilance will roll down like a watermelon. " They sacrifice part of their lives over and over again, listening to deception, slander, and insults. They built it themselves, but for whom is this market convenient ?! In the most convenient place where "people's real faces can be seen so clearly," they are deceived by their prey. There is no doubt that Bazar, written by Khurshid Dostmuhammad, is thought-provoking. The lives of its protagonists are of great interest to anyone. The author has arranged the events so skillfully that various questions arise during the reading process. One wonders how it will end. What about Fazil? Anyone who is not indifferent to the future today is tormented by the emotions that run through their hearts. At every step, he thinks about the problems in society. Although the work was written between 1988 and 1999, it is still relevant today. On the contrary, there are still many women around us who have a more tragic fate than Habiba. So what's the reason? Why is the number of divorces increasing? Perhaps the answer to these questions is really Fozilbek's imagination. It's just that people are acting like it's over. Thousands of families are falling apart because they don't understand each other when they marry someone they don't care about. Or the reason for early nikohmikan. Of course, there are many reasons. Until we find the answers to these questions, how many families on Earth will be divorced and how many children will be able to survive? Fazil thought a lot about not being one of them. In order to build a strong family and a prosperous life, he looked for a "suitable" person for himself. In my opinion, Qadriya was the most suitable for Fozil. Probably, the writer connected the destinies of two worthy young people to prevent them from rushing. Because the end of the work could have ended in tragedy. It was also possible that the two loving tongues could not reach each other. Why am I saying this because it is a very dangerous time. It is a time when people are selling for five coins, women who are giving up their children, and

indifferent people who say, "Honest people will help." It is important for the parent to do their duty to the child. But it is not good to have victims along the way. Who will be the victim? Two young people who don't care about each other. I read somewhere. "A girl should at least choose a mate in her life," he said. Indeed, we Uzbeks are a very strange people. The groom is coming, it's enough to have a well-fed family. They don't even ask for her heart. It is clear what will happen in the end. At the end of the play, which angered me, Qasim did not say a word when he offered his condolences to old Sabridin, saying, "Let us ask Qadriya for his heart." Probably a factor as to why they're doing so poorly. But what if Qadriya didn't like Fazil? Did we feel sorry for another woman? Fortunately, that didn't happen. The image of the mother who died while giving birth to Jigarbandi is still in Fozil's mind. Maybe it's because he doesn't smell his mother that he's talking to his imaginary mother. He asks if it was good that I didn't see injustice in the world. She is the only one who can feel the pain of giving birth to a piece of flesh. The author describes this process in an influential way. Not simply. Detailed lighting. Maybe it's a reminder to those who don't value their parents. A woman is a delicate creature. You just have to love him. Because it can never be understood. There is no need to talk much about the market. The reason is that it is foolish to expect something from a crowd that has not consulted. "There's a living person who thinks he's picking grain on his own." The people in the market are the same. There is nothing better than believing in the righteous and avoiding oneself and watching the nonsense of the innocent. Fozil's ancestors, who have spent their entire lives trying to make the market a success, have worked hard. Maybe eventually Fazil will finish the job. It is not surprising that he and his beloved wife started the society in the right direction. I was just hoping for that !!! No matter how difficult it may seem for a person to disappear in the middle or at the beginning of life, it is as if an old man wanders around in this ancient market of life. However, he is both lost and lost! Uzbek prose, freed from the oppression of social realism and the introduction of prototypes embedded in experience into artistic life, formed a new trend during independence, moving

away from Aristotle's view that "art is the depiction of external events." Man is the main theme, and humanism has shown itself. The climax, the course of events, was not transferred to any event, but to the evolution of the human mind.

In H. Dostmuhammad's novel "Bazar" this style is observed, in which the reality of life is closely depicted with the artistic reality, the experience takes precedence over the event.

Market .. pain .. hard .. or ..

The efforts of the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) to reach the level of "a believer will be found" will continue to live in peace, even if they are not visible today. When the clash of lust and faith in the human heart takes place in the market, who is the one who weighs the scales of the religion of the righteous and the vices of the ungodly ?! The work is entirely made up of signs and symbols, with the protagonist, the event, and even an inanimate object serving as a medium for contrast. At the same time, the name has two meanings: the market is a familiar sight in our society, a place of trade, a place where people's faces are revealed, a place of deceit, lust, deception; The market is a bridge between humanity and the world. Process. Initially, the writer, who began to introduce the personality of the protagonist Fozilbek, directly emphasizes the market, insisting on the truth in the form of "the market loses its imagination and loses itself." In fact, the market is mixed with the real picture in real life. Trying to convey the "Wisdom of Great Balance", the author portrays Fozilbek, Kadimbek, Von Suu, Zar-bobo, the market of life, which has nothing to do with reality, and Sabridin, Hodivoy, Khabiba Naynov, the market-process through legislators. In these prototypes, society and its ideas are clearly visible. Forms confusing thoughts between conflicting emotions in the destiny of no / decent people living in a decent time. In this case, anyone who is happy or on the verge of death is also deprived of experiences. Fozilbekkina, who is left alone in the world of market-loving and non-market-oriented analysis, is a stranger to the market of life. As the story unfolds in Fozilbek's mind, the image of the market in real life and the protagonist's reaction to the event are real. At the same time, in the realm

of imagination and life, the reader is so distracted that he forgets the truth. The hustle and bustle of the market is unbearable. As the author mentions the symbols in the right places, you will continue to walk around the market. If the market is noisy, the reading room is silent. In this contrast, people's thoughts and experiences are also categorized: those who are constantly following their desires, and those who stop halfway and try to understand something. In these views, in the mind of Fozilbek, who creates the 3rd way for himself, there is observation, and together with the hero, you analyze the ups and downs in the market, the sad, the oppressed, the remorseful and the ignorant. He will drown if the "worthy" do not save him from the "misery of a man's life in the market place." Doesn't the fact that a person, who is "rising from the power of Truth" until his last breath in the world of light, fall into the form of "life is movement", if he does not know how to swim, does he not understand that the current owns him?! Living as a role model in a large crowd; not being able to take advantage of a single opportunity, slapping his hand in his pocket; to continue the centuries-old tradition with "honor" for fear of failing to open a new path; to live quietly in the creation of destiny, not by determining, not by determining, not by creating; to make a mistake and place the risk of forgiveness on Him. You have to stop somewhere in the fast-paced market of the time. It is necessary to be able to find the desire to do so, it is also necessary to awaken the conscience! . In order to see the market-world, the market-dreams, the market, the nature of nature, it is necessary to stop the nafs, to look at it, to understand it. The work begins with the epigraph, "The head of the world is a flower, the head is a grave, and between the flower and the grave is a market," and a description of the market is given. The writer describes the bazaar as the most convenient place to see people's real faces in such a clear way, and skillfully uses conversations between the protagonist Fozilbek and Kasimbek, Diyorbek, Qadriya, Bakhtish, Von Suu, Egam grandparents to reveal the market. Fozilbek is unmarried despite being over 30 years old, for no apparent reason. He argues that finding a suitable girl to marry should not be done until a suitable one is found. This also indicates that Fozilbek is a spiritually mature, conscientious and

arrogant person in accordance with his name. As proof of this, at a time when he is ready to teach marriage by setting up a tent in the market in the hope of making more socks when he finds himself worthy, he intends to become a bridegroom to the reading room. In the play, the author not only points out the problems, but also points to their solutions, that is, "There are measures for all disasters, there are measures. Read books - everything is written. It's just a shame not to read them." In the play, the writer ruthlessly reveals the image of market people who do not know what knowledge, compassion, and honesty are. The play also covers current issues for today. He urges the reader to transcend lust. Anyone who wants to observe themselves from the outside should read the novel *The Market*. The work encourages the reader to think again, to look at the past, to be more vigilant.

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